

Challenges and opportunities associated with debt management observed and experienced by selected entrepreneurs in Bacoor City, Cavite

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Abstract

Business owners have the skills and knowledge to run their businesses in a successful way without ruining them. One of the greatest challenges business owners face is how to manage debt. Most business owners receive loans and borrow money without knowing areas in which they will be able to gain more funds to complete the payments of the debt. Most businesses fall due to their inability to pay their debt. This study, based on the narrative model, used a phenomenological strategy to first explain the perception of the effect of borrowing money and the challenges business owners face in running their businesses debt-free. The study employed respondents who have experienced struggles in paying their debts and struggles in running a business that has debts. Respondents' experiences and feedback were analyzed to answer the research questions presented in this study. The methodology utilized includes interviews with sixteen respondents around Bacoor, Cavite. Field notes were also collected during each interview. Data collected from each interview and the researchers' field notes were compared to identify themes. The themes synthesized from these research results helped answer the questions. This study found that the majority of the business owners who are in debt are small business owners; some of them are in debt because they lack funds to run their businesses, while others are in debt to keep their businesses going. Respondents in this study believed that in order for their businesses to run even though they lack resources, The best option is to borrow or receive a loan from cooperatives. Business owners need more information as to utilizing debt and having a long-lasting business opportunity. Furthermore, they need to know how to manage and eradicate debt in order to have a debt-free business.

Keywords: Challenges; Opportunities; Debt management; Entrepreneurs.

To cite this article:

Blanco, R. O., Antonio, M. A. P., Igoche, J. O., Manzano, A. B., & Valcorza, P. J. (2021). Challenges and opportunities associated with debt management observed and experienced by selected entrepreneurs in Bacoor City, Cavite. *SDCA Journal of Accountancy*, 2, 44-54.

Introduction

Debt management has been happening for an enormous amount of time, especially in developing countries around the world. As characterized, debt management is of high centrality for cash-related specialists and may be a complex administrative choice (Aslan et al., 2018). The uncertainty of trade cash flows may weaken the accessibility of financing, push commerce operations, and decrease future advancement prospects. In such circumstances, trying to find debt appeal will assist entrepreneurs to compose their back more easily and will in addition find ways of making their commitments less requesting to handle, such as reducing interest on their debt reimbursements or even solidifying the interest (Anoos et al., 2020). The extreme choice concerning debt management must be carefully examined for the business entrepreneurs to handle their budgetary obligations and for the company to continue its operations.

Insignificant choices about finance handling may influence the long-term monetary status of the company, which leads to incompetence and denial of future growth (Brodeur et al., 2020).

A business that is bound by debt is tough to operate. Budgetary trouble influences the company's operations circumstances, attacking indeed our transient contemplations and gradually declining our connections with the individuals that encompass us (Guinigundo, 2016). Debt management has been one of the key variables in overseeing the reserves of a business. Adrian (2019) noted that debt management is of macroeconomic importance. Realizing the importance that stressed the longer-term advantage of both borrowers and investors in promoting their debt transparency as reliable, stable, and cost-effective financing of public goods. According to Gray (2020), debt settlement is a service offered by third-party companies that can try to reduce one's debt by negotiating settlements with your creditors or debt collectors. As issues continue to arise, small-scale businesses tend to shut down faster than larger companies since they cannot afford continuous losses and higher debts. Knowledge of debt management is important for every business entrepreneur to learn.

Literature Review

Bolognesi et al. (2020) observe that many citizens in the United States are highly literate but rely heavily on debt, engage frequently in expensive short- and long-term money management, and display shockingly low levels of financial literacy. Unable to cope with continuous debts, recommendations for financial wellness programs to support the decision-makers of the company are being discussed in the study to increase awareness among business owners about the financial resilience of their businesses. A study by Yuan and Motohashi (2014) using a sample of Chinese listed companies showed that the total debt ratio had a negative impact on fixed investment. This is because a firm with a high debt ratio can potentially channel most of its income towards debt servicing, thereby forgoing investment through internal funds. Therefore, the risk of a small-scale enterprise increases when more debt is employed in its capital structure. The study uncovered that the major causes of debt among small-scale enterprises were a lack of advice on business type and finances, a lack of knowledge on the type of business, and poor methods of keeping financial records. Inappropriate debt management practices put these businesses at risk of liquidity and, hence, affect their performance.

Since small-scale enterprises have lower income and are sometimes limited, they will always be prone to risks that can affect their capital structure. According to Lusardi et al. (2020), there is a need for support in debt management for small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) to improve their financial health, but this study suggested that advice about what business type SMEs are in, and their financial conditions was needed. Having knowledge of what business type they have is a very important practice, rather than keeping their financial health to themselves.

Debt management is one of the most important factors to consider when running a business. Without functional debt management, there is bound to be misallocation and misappropriation of resources that could be used to promote the development of the economy with a view to attaining growth (Saleh et al., 2015). Weak debt management leads to the existence of challenges that are policy, institutional, and operational that may affect the business's future. Business entrepreneurs face challenges that include the emergence of brand-new markets and economic conditions, as well as the obscure financial boundaries that can affect dealing with developing competitors. A functional research debt strategy can save small-scale industries time in decision-making and a possible increase in budget that can be used for the improvement of the business.

Debt settlement is a practice that allows a person to pay a lump sum that is typically less than the amount he or she owes to resolve or settle one's debt. It is a service that is typically offered by third-party companies that claim to reduce one's debt by negotiating a settlement with his or her creditor. Paying off a debt for less than you owe may sound great at first, but debt settlement can be risky, potentially impacting credit scores or even costing more money. According to Gray (2020), one should know about how debt

settlement works, its pros and cons, and how it could affect his or her credit. There can be a few pros to debt settlement, but you should carefully consider the potential risks of debt settlement as well. The advantages are that it can lower the debt amount, help him or her avoid bankruptcy, and get creditors and collectors off one's back. On the other hand, the negative sides are that one's creditors may not agree to negotiate, which could end up with more debt with charged fees, even if a whole debt was not settled, and it could negatively impact his or her credit. Gray (2020) also discussed the alternatives to debt settlement by negotiating their own settlement, transferring balances, and seeking non-profit credit counseling. Reducing debt is the first goal one should attempt to achieve. Debt settlement may be very risky, but it is better than filing for bankruptcy or insolvency. It is said that hiring professionals or third-party companies is a big help, but other studies suggest that the owner himself should deal with the debt problem. Debt settlement with third-party considerations to fix the debt compared to handling it on one's own both have their pros and cons. Choosing the best appropriate debt management practice is a must because knowing the situation that gives him or her a favorable state should get your company in the best financial state.

Money borrowing is considered a normal process necessary for the attainment of the vision and missions of the business. Zaragoza and Arceño's (2017) study implies that the consequences of borrowing money from lending institutions affect not only the business but the employee's performance as well. Kravchenko (2016) then concluded that lending to banks has a positive impact on future capital in small-scale industries, particularly those that have a stable income. However, Aldaba (2012) underscored that SMEs had been unable to access funds because of their limited track record, limited acceptable collateral, and inadequate financial statements and business plans. Banks tend to turn down financial requests from small microenterprises because of poor credit history, insufficient collateral, inadequate sales, income or cash flow, unstable business types, and poor business plans.

Having limited sources and possible economic problems may tend to be the best or worst choice of applying for a loan in a bank if business entrepreneurs in small and micro enterprises are beneficial to the company. Deciding on where to apply for one's loan is vital for any business entrepreneur to consider saving cash revenue in the business. It will allocate a future income to budget for the allocation on the deadline of payment. The small microbusiness has limited cash flow compared to medium and large enterprises; one of our possible solutions is to thoroughly research whether applying for a loan is beneficial for the small micro-enterprises in dealing with their debt management (Kravchenko, 2011).

Statement of the Problem

This study sought to determine the challenges and opportunities associated in debt management by selected entrepreneurs in Bacoor. Specifically, this study aimed to answer the following questions:

1. How do respondents handle the challenges associated in debt management?
2. What are the challenges encountered by the respondents that prompt them to acquire a loan for additional capital?
3. Based on the interview, what recommendations are necessary to handle the challenges associated in debt management by small and micro-entrepreneurs?

Methodology

The researchers based their study on a qualitative research approach and used a phenomenological strategy to explain to business entrepreneurs of small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) near Zapote, Bacoor, and Cavite about their loans and a thorough study of their debt management.

Research Design

The narrative model occurs over extended periods and compiles information as it happens (Elçi & Devran, 2014). This study uses an oral history approach to gather personal reflections on events and debt management experiences. Like a story narrative, it takes subjects to a starting point and reviews situations as obstacles or challenges occur. Although the final narrative does not always remain in chronological order (McAlpine, 2016), the researchers focus the questions for the respondents within the statement of the problem. The narrative method is effective in business-related transactions as the research focuses on debt management for small entrepreneurs. It helps to identify past-related events up to current transactions, seeking information on their problems and solutions narrated by the entrepreneurs to manage their debts.

Qualitative Research Approach

This study used a phenomenological strategy to explain the challenges faced with debt management. Through careful consideration, planning, and research, researchers have the unique ability to survey their audience's experiences and gather insights from the various challenges they experienced and how they dealt with those challenges. Qualitative research grants us access to different immersive user experiences, allowing the researchers to develop an empathic perspective of their audience as a guide for the research.

To employ an empathic perspective, project objectives must be well defined and understood. Gaining this perspective helps to prove or disprove any initial assumptions or personal bias toward end-users. This perspective also helps to uncover useful insights and opportunities that are not readily apparent. Increased emotional capacity and an understanding of the end users' motivations and behaviors are also critical to framing the problem and furthering opportunities for the effective application of their challenges with debt. The development of user empathy goes beyond what the users are saying and, more importantly, delves into what they are doing and why. Additionally, user empathy plays an integral part in defining research strategy, tactics, and success metrics.

The insights uncovered in the following research investigation have been gathered through various sources of primary qualitative research and immersive experiences of observation and documentation. Employing multiple research methodologies allowed critical patterns, behaviors, and influences to surface, thereby defining the user's experience. Once gathered, a foundation of user perspectives formulated the final direction of the investigation and determined which methods of research would help extract further information. The intended purpose of the research conducted for the investigation was to provide insight as to how business owners could improve the existing challenges faced by small and micro-entrepreneurs around Zapote, Bacoar. It was intended with at least 15 respondents in the area, specifically focusing on those who have challenges with debt and those primarily using business loans as the primary means of financing their businesses.

Research Instrument

The researchers used a scripted questionnaire formulated and directly connected to the statement of the problem in order to get the information needed in this study. During the face-to-face interview, audio and video recordings have been used for documentation and review of the data gathered.

Interview

While data collection and data analysis activities were intricately woven together throughout this phase of the study, for clarity, they would be described separately. The primary sources of data for this study were face-to-face interviews.

For this study, qualitative interviews were the primary method of data collection because they were deemed appropriate by the researchers. Qualitative interviewing generally includes data in the form of words rather than numbers (Busetto et al., 2020). Interviews also allow for the triangulation of information obtained from other sources (Lincoln & Guba, 1985). For this research, all interviews were conducted via interception and approached in open public environments in Zapote Market and around St. Dominic College of Asia (SDCA). The researchers interviewed those who seemed fit to meet the criteria for respondents in the designated location. Further, any reserved respondents were contacted to have the interview in a suitable and comfortable place. As the first step in the interview process, respondents were reminded of the purpose of the study, research procedures, the expected questionnaire, their right to withdraw from the study at any time, and the protection of confidentiality.

Developed from initial assumptions and biases about the users' behaviors and motivations, the following list of questions was designed to guide a series of conversation-based interviews to prove or disprove their existence. The interviews specifically focused on gauging respondents' financial background, level of experience, current education debt situation, and financial capability. In order to remain unbiased in their questioning, respondents were permitted to dictate the general direction of the interview. None of the respondents interviewed were compensated for their time.

1. What is the type of your business?
2. Are you the owner of the business? If yes, do you have co-owners?
3. How many employees does this business holds?
4. How much was your starting capital?
5. What type of loan do you usually avail? How much is the interest rate it bears?
6. Have you experienced harassment upon failing to pay on or before the due date of your loan?
7. Have you experienced facing revenue ups and downs and financial instability? If yes, what are the methods you use to pay for your debts?
8. In what way have you come up with your starting capital?
9. Did it turn out that you needed to borrow additional capital from banks or any other financial institution?
10. What were the reasons you considered before applying for a loan?
11. Do you have any outstanding loan for the business?
12. What recommendations can you give to small and micro entrepreneurs who have handling challenges associated with debt management?

Respondents

The researchers conducted the interview with business owners of small and medium enterprises (SMEs) around Bacoor, Cavite. Purposive sampling based on intended research outcomes was performed according to the defined criteria. Respondents interviewed via interception were approached in open public environments in Bacoor and around St. Dominic College of Asia (SDCA). Specific locations were targeted for their demographic concentration. Referred respondents were initially contacted by phone or e-mail, and a suitable time and place were arranged. Health protocols and guidelines would also be strictly maintained as the interview commences until it is finished. A total of 15 respondents was conducted by the interview.

The objective of interviewing and intercepting was to develop an initial foundation of user empathy and gain key insights on the user's own perspective on the challenges they face in debt management.

Ethnography was specifically chosen for its ability to access valuable qualitative information. The collected data was distilled through a synthesis process and triangulated for validity. The findings from this methodology were used to guide future research efforts and provide direction for the next phases of the design process.

Data Collection Analysis

The research analysis conducted in the interview is subjected to three separate phases. First, the researcher's transcripts were reviewed several times, searching for recurring regularities and uncommon answers that are still acceptable for further discussion. The researchers also highlight the quotes and phrases from the interviews that may seem significant to the study. Using the constant comparative method (Glaser & Strauss, 2012), the researcher then went to double-check the data gathered until categories emerged that were fully classified but still differentiated by the aspect of each answer. The researcher named these categories, emphasized the important information in the transcripts, and placed sections in labeled documents representing each question and answer from the interview conducted. Second, the researchers brought together the coded interviews and field notes and looked for relationships within and across the data sources. Graphs and tables were developed to compare various interviews. As tentative categories emerged, the researcher tested them against the data (Merriam & Tisdell, 2015). Lastly, the researchers then finalized and completely organized the categories until themes solidified for discussions and conclusions.

Results and Discussion

The primary purpose of this study is to understand the perceptions of the selected entrepreneurs in Bacoor, Cavite, based on the results of the research questionnaire. Respondents' experiences and feedback added insight to the research questions posed in this study. By listening and analyzing the experiences of these entrepreneurs, valuable information was obtained about the challenges and opportunities associated with debt management by selected entrepreneurs in Bacoor, Cavite.

A total of fourteen out of the fifteen respondents are business owners, and the majority of them serve in other capacities. Respondent 5 works as a staff member in his aunt's business, not as an owner. Six of the fifteen respondents do not have employees whom they pay; instead, they depend on family members for assistance, while the rest have less than ten employees. They each have their own stories to tell about how they got started in business. Respondent 1 said, *"I was trying to settle some unpaid bills and decided to try some graphic designing courses. I realized it was something I could do best and that's how I started the business."* Respondent 2 stated that he started his business just by going out. He honestly said that he did not have any idea what he was doing, but he was willing to learn all that he needed to know. As to respondent 4, he said, *"The first thing I did was to locate my capital and determination to pursue my venture. I have conducted a survey to determine who would be my target market until I've come to the conclusion that it could be children or the elderly."* Generally, they began by learning how to make their first move, finding capital by looking for creditors, then promoting their goods and selling out.

Others simply try their luck with their friends or by relocating to a new place, like respondent 7, who has a friend who credits them with rice to sell directly from the rice mill, which is where they get their stocks. Before her husband's parents died, they gave them their house, which they have turned into a shop. Respondent 9, who is from the Bicol region, only tried to live in Cavite with his wife to make a living. They have sold their carabaos so they could use them as capital. He has a cousin who previously worked in a vulcanizing shop, and he was the one who encouraged them to open up even a small shop.

Capital Beginning

Aside from knowing the basics, it is also important to know the capital of the business, which is significant because it is the portion of an asset that can be used to repay its depositors as well as to invest in a variety of items in order to create value. The majority of the respondents had the same response: they had some savings, but not nearly enough, so they needed to take out a loan to help them start the business they wanted. They had to take out a loan, borrow from cooperatives, or even borrow from Indian tenants, also known as the “5-6.” They had to pay a loan, which was usually repayable in three (3) to six (6) months depending on their preference, or to their co-lenders that they had to pay every day or anytime they had money. Since they do not have enough sources of income, they still need to borrow from other financial institutions for their additional capital.

Respondent 1 said that they had a capital of 70,000 pesos, while Respondent 2 had 30,000 pesos and Respondent 3 had 45,000 pesos, all coming from their savings. Respondent 4 said, *“I used my husband’s rental income from his commercial building. He divided it between the two of us, and that is now my monthly salary. That is the amount of money I saved and used as capital (25,000 pesos).”* Respondent 5, who owns an accounting firm, stated that they had 100,000 pesos as their beginning capital and 10,000 pesos for Respondent 6.

Another entrepreneur, Respondent 7, has 80,000 pesos as their beginning capital and has a supplier that credits all of their stocks to them. Other respondents receive financial assistance from their respective family members, such as money from their daughter and son, from close friends, and even in other financial institutions, they all range from 10,000 to 40,000 pesos. While the others, like Respondent 8, needed investors for his additional capital, he had 500,000 pesos as his beginning capital. Respondent 9, who have sold their carabao, had 150,000 pesos as their beginning capital. They had to give up something in exchange for a higher expected return on their investment in the business; Respondent 9 also stated, *“So many people are asking if we sell tires, so we’ve decided to borrow money for an additional business to sell mags and tires.”* Respondent 10 had a capital of 10,000 pesos coming from a loan in a local cooperative. Respondent 11 had a starting capital of 100,000 pesos, coming from her and her son’s savings. Respondent 12 had a starting capital of 500,000 pesos, which came from a local rural bank with a term of two (2) years and a 3% per annum interest rate. Respondent 13 had a starting capital of 25,000 pesos coming from her savings and a loan from an Indian. Respondent 14 had a capital of 50,000 pesos coming from her savings and her daughter’s from abroad. Respondent 15 had a capital of 250,000 pesos coming from their life savings.

Business Loans

Several entrepreneurs who took part in the interview had outstanding business loans, and the reasons they considered taking out a loan were to start their own business and the costs of living, such as energy and food. Respondent 1, who did not have enough money at the time, contemplated taking out a loan of 25,000 pesos because he realized he needed computers and gadgets for his business. Respondent 2 wants to have enough financial backing to make sure that his business will thrive. He borrowed 10,000 pesos from the bank and paid it in a month. Respondent 3 borrowed money from a private lender for three (3) months with 5% interest per month. Respondents 4 and 6 used to get loans from their siblings, relatives, or friends, and also stated that they considered the necessity first before taking out a loan. As for Respondent 5, her aunt usually gets her loan in the bank. *“My aunt used to wonder if getting a loan was a smart idea for purchasing new office equipment because her old equipment was obsolete.”* Her aunt borrowed 50,000 pesos for three (3) years to pay with 12% interest.

Respondent 7 stated that what they loan is their inventory which is 100,000 a month and with no interest. She added that they do not have any loans or debts now besides their supplies. As for respondent 8, he had a loan of 200,000 pesos with 5% interest per month and he only pays the interest until the principal is paid. He still has outstanding loans but only from those who invested in his business, *“I still need to pay them back, the investments from my friends.”*

Respondents 9 and 11 to 15 have no outstanding debts; as for Respondent 10, she borrowed money from a cooperative that is 10 months old to pay for 30,000 pesos. Respondent 9 once borrowed money from a cousin's friend who is a money lender, and the first estimated how much they could pay back if they took out the loan, and luckily, their cousin's friend is so generous that she gave them a very low interest rate of 6% for a 200,000 peso loan. Respondents 11 to 14 have had the experience of having a loan from a bank normally ranging from 10,000 pesos and above. What they thought at the time was that they needed more capital for the business and for their needs, but because of the pandemic, they have stopped borrowing money. *"What we receive from the business is often what we use for day-to-day living, even though there are shortfalls sometimes."* Respondent 15's business is on a long-term loan for their inventories with an amount of 1,000,000 pesos.

Loan Solutions

Different solutions amidst the loan crisis were then gathered from 15 respondents. The majority of the respondents rely on their net income for the payment of their debts. Respondents 1, 2, 3, 5, 10, 14, and 15 said that business loans must be considered paid for by the sales they produce in the business. Respondents 4, 6, and 8 said that other than revenue, they use research such as surveys and quality controls to maximize their debt management. Respondent 4 said confidently while conducting the interview, *"Yes, it was effective to solve if I got feedback from other people. If there's something wrong or missing, I can make some plans to fix it. As they say, there is always room for improvement so I can get a higher income to pay my debts."* Respondent 8 added, *"I make sure that I have many customers and I make sure of the quality of my product, so I make more effort in marketing and quality control of my products. If I lose customers, how can I pay everyone who invested in me? I will have a hard time then."* Respondent 7 said that other than income, they use investments and reservations for the payment to continue handling their debts well. He said, *"Every afternoon we deposit our sales in the bank so the check will not bounce back when it is already due,"* and jokingly added, *"Just always deposit it in the bank because if you hold on to the money, you might spend it somewhere else. You might spend it on Shopee and Lazada deliveries instead."*

Respondents 9, 11, 12, 13, and 14 suggested that controlling budgeting and savings when debt has been incurred can be a solution for paying the loans on time. Respondent 9 said, *"At first, we were really tightening our budget. We only buy those that we need, and every time we sell our stocks, we save half for payments. We don't spend anything from the money we saved for payments."* A partner said that they always plan for the distribution of income with expenses and debt so they will pay the debts on time. In addition, no one experienced harassment because all of them paid their debts on time.

Advice to Co-Entrepreneurs

Business entrepreneurs gave advice to other aspiring entrepreneurs on starting a loan. Here are some of the responses:

R1: *Make sure that when you apply for a loan, you are sure that you will be able to pay it back without putting your business in jeopardy.*

R2: *To my co-entrepreneurs, taking a loan isn't a bad idea as long as you are sure that you will be able to pay up the loan. It would be extremely beneficial in terms of establishing a startup capital or providing a boost to keep a company going.*

R3: *Before you acquire a loan, make sure you will be able to pay it back.*

R4: *Consider paying off your debt as soon as possible so that interest does not accrue.*

R5: *Don't take on debt unless it's absolutely necessary, and if you do decide to take out a loan, make sure you have a projection for the monthly amortization budget.*

R6: *My suggestion is that getting a loan isn't so bad as long as they pay it back. It takes a long time to pay it off, so it's best to pay that off every now and then, even if it's just for a small amount; at the very least, the debt is being paid off. It doesn't matter whether the amount is small or large; what matters is that you know how to pay because you'll need it and they'll put their faith in you. I'm aware that many successful businesses begin with debts, and there's nothing wrong with that.*

R7: *You can deposit the sales immediately because there's a chance you'll spend it elsewhere.*

R8: *If you take out a loan, make sure you can repay it. And if you have access to large loans, don't borrow more than you need. Just get what you need because spending money is easy, but repaying loans is tough.*

R9: *All I can say is that if they need to borrow money, they should look for a low interest rate so they don't have trouble paying it back, and they should make sure to allocate the payment by their income. Others simply sat on the money like one-day millionaires. We were very frugal in order to repay the loan. Our lives became better after we completed our loan repayment.*

R10: *Pay off your debt immediately so you can borrow money again and pay on a monthly basis to prevent debt accumulation.*

R11: *Spend within your means so you don't have to borrow too much, also borrow accordingly.*

R12: *If at all possible, avoid taking out new loans because they are extremely difficult to repay, particularly now that there is a pandemic, but if you really need to, there is no problem but plan the payment, budget for debt and for daily expenses.*

R13: *If it was just me I really didn't want to have debt because it's hard to pay especially now that there's a pandemic. I am in debt because I need an increase in capital, and if you are planning to borrow money, you need to think carefully and please pay off the debt right away.*

R14: *There is nothing wrong with borrowing as long as you know how to pay and know how to handle money correctly.*

R15: *If you really need to borrow money, it's alright, but think carefully about what kind of borrowing to do. It's hard to get into debt, so if you want to do business, be sure and just have perseverance.*

This study presented the results of interviews with 15 entrepreneurs from Bacoor, Cavite. Findings in this study were presented in different categories that corresponded with the primary themes that emerged from the results; categories within this study helped to support and provide more insights on the research topic.

Respondents in this study clearly stated the various challenges they face in running a business, so the best option is to take up a loan or borrow from cooperatives to make their business function appropriately. Feedback from respondents also supported the notion that in order for their business to go smoothly without having a breakdown, business owners need to gain knowledge on debt management, including how to reduce the risk of debt and how to pay their debtors in due time.

Owning a small business is a very big responsibility. It faces many challenges; the owner himself faces unsettled debts, so there is great trouble because of the economy's breakdown. According to Anos et al. (2020), most of the small entrepreneurs in Danao City do not practice the generally accepted standards on the financial management and control of the business, which poses some threats to its sustainability, considering that their paramount size, the volume of assets, and revenue earned are relatively low or minimal. One of the disadvantages of SMEs is that most of them rely on their sheer wits and luck without any support for their financial status, such as accounting, auditing, and management control, because they have limited or simply lack the resources to do so. In certain circumstances, they had no money left to pay their wage bills, contractors, and other kinds of bills, so most of them chose to go for a business loan or debt to pay the expenses of the business. A possible continuous loss or deficit in income may be a possible choice when applying for debt. Even applying for a loan sometimes poses a risk to the business. In certain cases, business owners are unable to pay their debt. Continuous penalties arising from the obligation may incur losses that may cause small and microenterprises to shut down. The researchers discussed appropriate

actions if entrepreneurs cannot pay their debts on time. Debt settlement programs give a chance of security that debt can be settled.

Conclusion and Recommendations

Based on the findings, the researchers conclude that entrepreneurs could incur additional borrowings or avail credits for their operations as additional funds. Though they avail their credit through banks, cooperatives, and small and individual lenders, the interest rate, terms of payment, and their capacity to pay are also major concerns for the entrepreneurs. Nonetheless, all have complied and are complying with their financial obligations.

The borrowing of funds is a traditional form of business operation; that means debt management is one of the common challenges that business entrepreneurs face in their operation, and that means exercising frugality is needed in the business operation. The opportunities brought about by the borrowing are that the business can go through expansion of the operation, purchase of capital equipment, and generate more sales. Although careful decisions must be considered first because these are high risks that can cause problems rather than a solution, Entrepreneurs should excel in their business operations to be able to pay off their debt. Feedback from customers and quality control can help the business maintain its standards and even increase sales.

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